

CONTINUING EDUCATION IN UZBEKISTAN AS A REQUIREMENT OF THE TIMES

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ABSTRACT

Continuity of the formation are considered in the article as a condition of the provision quality formation, problems for ensuring the successful unceasing formation, as well as the importance of unceasing formation in increasing quality formation and formations of the future teacher.

The changes taking place in the field of education in the modern world are associated with a change in the educational paradigm, the essence of which is the transition from the concept of basic education, designed to equip a person with knowledge and skills, to the concept of lifelong education, which should ensure constant renewal knowledge by the dynamics of change: socio-economic and cultural. This concept is now accepted by almost all the advanced countries of the world. It promotes adult education to a defining position in the socio-economic development of the country. Traditional basic education, received at the beginning of life, does not keep pace with the changes in the world, fundamentally cannot provide a

person for life with the knowledge, skills, ability, ties, and qualities necessary for him to effectively fulfill various social roles. The concept of lifelong education, adopted by almost all advanced countries, promotes adult education to a defining position in the main areas of socio-economic development of the modern world, including in Uzbekistan. At the present stage, social relations based on a market economy are being formed in the republic. Our model of transition to market relations is based on taking into account the specific conditions and characteristics of the republic: traditions, customs, way of life. The new conditions of the labor market dictated the main directions of the development of the education system in the republic.

Continuity of education is an important principle introduced into the National Program for Personnel Training. It means that education begins in preschool institutions, continues in nine-year school, and then in academic lyceums and vocational colleges. Further - higher education with two levels - for bachelors and masters, postgraduate - doctoral studies. At the same time, the continuity of education means that having started working, a person can continue to study. For this, various forms of retraining and advanced training of personnel are being created. State policy in the field of education is based on the following principles: - humanistic, democratic nature of education and upbringing; - continuity and continuity of secondary specialized, professional, higher and postgraduate education; - the secular nature of the education system; - general accessibility of education within the state educational standards; - the unity and differentiation of the approach to the choice of training programs; - encouragement of giftedness and talent; - a combination of state and public administration in the higher education system; - integration of higher education, science, and industry.¹ At present, high requirements are imposed on the personality of a specialist, such as the ability to be creative, quick adaptation, the ability to continuous professional growth, self-development, and self-improvement. Based on all of the above requirements, vocational education should be aimed at creating conditions for ensuring the personal and professional growth of future specialists, developing their ability to

independently solve life and professional problems. Since the development of professionalism is influenced not only by the individual characteristics of the teacher but also by the characteristics of his environment. In most cases, continuing education is seen as a condition for ensuring the quality of education. The idea of lifelong education acquires a special meaningful content in our time, and the continuity of education in modern conditions is considered as a fundamental requirement and a necessary condition for ensuring the quality of the processes and results of education.

At the present time, the signs (they are also called principles) are defined that characterize the continuity of education: - coverage of education throughout a person's life; - understanding of the educational system as a holistic one, including preschool education, basic, sequential, repeated, parallel education, uniting and integrating all its levels and forms; - horizontal integration: home - neighbors - local social sphere - society - world of work - mass media - recreational, cultural, religious organizations, etc; - the connection between the subjects studied; - vertical integration: the relationship between the individual stages of education - preschool, school, postschool; between different levels and objects within separate stages; between different social roles realized by a person at certain stages of his life; between different qualities of human development (such qualities of a temporary nature as physical, moral, intellectual development, etc.); - improving the ability to learn; stimulating motivation to study;

¹ Begimkulov U.Sh. Some aspects of the system of continuing education in the Republic of Uzbekistan. - Tashkent, 2010

creation of appropriate conditions and atmosphere for learning.² The task of providing real tests and grounds for self-determination as ensuring successful continuous education, including the choice of future professional activity, comes to the fore. The modern dynamics of life require general education not from "coaching" in mathematics, physics, languages, but the creation of conditions for the formation of key competencies that allow the graduate to quickly master new professions and subject areas in the process of obtaining higher education. These competencies include the ability to act autonomously, communication, the ability to work with a problem, that is, "design competence" associated with isolating a problem, translating it into a task, creating and implementing a project. Awareness of these problems led us to the idea of developing a social practice program that would "increase the chance of eventfulness" - providing senior students with the experience of responsible full-fledged action in the open-world - action with intention, planning, coordination of resources, obtaining a product in demand and the process of reflecting on the results. The program assumes that schoolchildren are involved in a real project of an actor in the economic sphere to create a socially demanded product. In the process of this social and professional practice, a high school student interacts with carriers of different professional skills, mastering some of them, and realizes the difference between general education and education aimed at professional self-determination.

² Lapkov A. V. MOU "General education lyceum № 6" Perspektiva", Krasnoyarsk, Russia, p. 31.7.

The implementation of the program is effective not only for lyceum students: the lyceum acquires partners from different spheres of activity (business, politics, social services), which ultimately determines its image as an active subject of a micro-district, a city.³ One of the main goals of lifelong education is to expand and diversify educational services that complement basic school or university education. Continuing education is equated with adult education since we are talking about various forms of retraining, advanced training, and cultural level of people who have overcome the usual age of basic education.

The national model and program is a strategically thought-out, scientifically grounded model (concept), which is very sensitive to the trends and nuances of the country's socio-economic development. Thus, the National Model makes us constantly look for the most effective ways to implement it. The positive results of the reform, characteristic of all levels of education, include: - the progressive development of the educational system as a single educational, scientific, and production complex based on state and non-state educational institutions, the formation of a competitive environment in the field of education and personnel training with the involvement of all sources of funding (state and non-state), the development and introduction into practice of real mechanisms for attracting extra-budgetary funds, including foreign investment, in the system of continuous education and training; In this regard, the question arises about the effectiveness of

³ Education reforms in Uzbekistan in the light of human development objectives. Formation of a national model of education.

the forms of implementation of lifelong education, which still needs to be investigated. It is obvious that lifelong education is not the next stage in the development of the education system, but acts as a necessary component of the process of integrating science, education, and production. Higher education of the republic solves the priority task of training qualified teachers of the appropriate level and profile, competitive in the labor market, competent, responsible, fluent in their profession and focused on related areas of activity, capable of effective work in their specialty at the level of world standards. This task requires scientific support of goals, content, methods, means, and organizational forms of education, training, and personal development in higher education based on the use of the achievements of science, technology, and innovative technologies. The solution to the problems of higher professional education is impossible without raising the pedagogical intellectual culture, without overcoming the established stereotypes, conservatism in pedagogical science and practice. These problems are directly related to the development and implementation of innovative technologies in the educational process. Thus, the formation of the lifelong education system is based on two interrelated trends: the invasion of production into the sphere of basic training and, conversely, the penetration of training into the production

process. In the conditions of the emerging new information and communication society, innovative technologies burst into the system of lifelong education with their undoubted advantages and indisputable disadvantages, which requires appropriate adaptation of the subjects to this. This article in the context of the ongoing large-scale reforms in the Republic of Uzbekistan and the need for an accelerated renewal of fixed assets, leasing is of particular importance as a form of financing the investment activities of economic entities.⁴ The composition and interconnection of education components should have a flexible structure and functionality, adapting to the peculiarities of the specific content of the environment, the needs and abilities of the learners. Continuing education is also of great importance for improving the quality of education and the formation of a future teacher. The idea of limiting the boundaries of "civil society" and "state" was proposed by the German philosopher G. Hegel. It should be noted that society and "civil society" is generally a state term.⁵ This approach allows you to reveal and develop the professional qualities of the future teacher, which will be necessary for the chosen profession, and also helps to solve various problems that arise in the learning process. All this allows the teacher to become a unique innovator, a productive technologist of teaching and upbringing.

⁴ Tolibjonovich, M. T., & Rahimjon o'g'li, G. O. (2021). PREREQUISITES FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF A LEASING MECHANISM IN PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP. *International Engineering Journal For Research & Development*, 6(SP), 5-5.

⁵ Nasriddinovich, A. A. (2021). STRUCTURE, MODELS AND CHARACTERISTICS OF CIVIL SOCIETY. *STRUCTURE*, 7(4).

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